

Bondarenko Daniil Vladimirovich,
Senior Lecturer, Department of Finance and Credit,
Institute of economics and management.
V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,
Simferopol, Russian Federation.

EVOLUTION OF CORPORATE FINANCIAL STRATEGY: INTEGRATION OF A VALUE-BASED APPROACH AND RISK-BASED MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

VUCA

This article provides a comprehensive study of the transformation of the corporate financial management paradigm in the context of the challenges of a VUCA and the accelerated digitalization of the economy. A critical comparative analysis of classical and modern concepts reveals a systemic gap between long-term value creation goals and operational efficiency, as well as fragmented approaches to risk management integration. As a methodological response to these challenges, an original integrated process model (mechanism) for improving the effectiveness of corporate financial management has been developed and thoroughly substantiated. Its scientific novelty lies in the synthesis of strategic value planning, operational risk control, and digital analytical platforms into a single adaptive management framework with a central role played by an active financial platform. The model represents a dynamic architecture where financial strategy is transformed from a formal document into a living, data-driven process. The paper demonstrates that modern financial management is evolving from a functional support function to a key strategic competency that determines a corporation's sustainability and competitiveness. The results provide a theoretical foundation and practical roadmap for building a financial architecture that is resilient to crises and capable of continuously generating long-term value for all stakeholder groups.

Keywords: corporate finance, financial strategy, strategic financial management, corporate value management, integrated risk management, digital transformation, adaptive management, process model, digital platform, sustainable development.

VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, Ambiguity).

[1-14].

1.

2.

(«
»),

»,«

»,«

3.

()

4.

1) ;

2) (« »);

VUCA-3) ;

4) ;

1. - ;

XX (Value Based Management — VBM). ;

() ;

() (Balanced Scorecard — BSC) . ;

ERM), - (Enterprise Risk Management — COSO ERM) ;

(VBM, BSC, ERM) ;

2.

3.

« .1) »
(AI/ML- ,OLAP-
,RPA),
(PESTEL-)
KPI, «
» —
(NPV, IRR),
(ERM)
(ERM).
, ERM-
(, VaR — Value at Risk),
, compliance).
, ERM
() Key Risk Indicators (KRI).

.1.

9. — 2024. — 1(66). — С. 76-88. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2024-1-76-88. — EDN IGTMTL.
10. // — 2007. — 1. — С. 198-201. — EDN NSCKKB.
11. , 1999. — 111 .
12. : : 2 . / . ; [.] — . — 1997. — XXX, 497 .
13. [.]. — : « », 2017. — 632 . — ISBN 978-5-9909795-9-8. — EDN ZDRPXL.
14. Ensuring economic security at different levels of economic management / D. D. Burkaltseva, M. N. Dudin, V. E. Reutov [et al.]. — Simferopol : POLIPRINT, 2018. — 194 p. — ISBN 978-5-6041133-5-6. — EDN UXEWGY.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Vliyaniye korporativnogo upravleniya na strukturu kapitala otechestvennykh kompaniy / Ye. A. Fedorova, V. G. Komletsova, M. K. Tregubova [i dr.] // *Finansy: teoriya i praktika*. — 2022. — Т. 26, 2. — С. 25-37. — DOI 10.26794/2587-5671-2022-26-2-25-37. — EDN HSVTDE.
2. Vorobyov, Yu. N. *Finansovaya strategiya predpriyatiya* / Yu. N. Vorobyov, E. I. Vorobyova, N. V. Il'inykh. — Simferopol' : Tavriya, 2006. — 118 s. — ISBN 966-435-016-8. — EDN UAGASH.
3. Vorobyova, E. I. Gosudarstvennaya finansovaya strategiya Rossiyskoy Federatsii: teoreticheskiye aspekty i praktika realizatsii / E. I. Vorobyova, O. G. Blazhevich // *Nauchnyy vestnik: finansy, banki, investitsii*. — 2024. — 3(68). — С. 17-33. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2024-3-17-33. — EDN NEOKGD.
4. Izmaylova, M. A. ESG-povestka v Rossii: sovremennoye razvitiye i mekhanizm transformatsii rossiyskikh kompaniy. Chast' 2 / M. A. Izmaylova // *MIR (Modernizatsiya. Innovatsii. Razvitiye)*. — 2023. — Т. 14, 4. — С. 538-553. — DOI 10.18184/2079-4665.2023.14.4.538-553. — EDN PLXLLP.
5. Kalafatov, E. A. Rol' finansovoy strategii dlya sel'skokhozyaystvennykh predpriyatiy v usloviyakh neopredelennosti vneshney sredy / E. A. Kalafatov // *Nauchnyy vestnik: finansy, banki, investitsii*. — 2020. — 4(53). — С. 27-36. — DOI 10.37279/2312-5330-2020-4-27-36. — EDN SHMMFP.
6. Makusheva, Ye. V. Klassicheskaya teoriya stoimosti i teoriya tsenoobrazovaniya A. Marshalla / Ye. V. Makusheva, Ye. S. Makarova, Ye. A. Kravchenko // *Nauka bez granits*. — 2021. — 2(54). — С. 90-95. — EDN WCQIAR.
7. Otsenka i obespecheniye finansovoy bezopasnosti, ustoychivogo razvitiya na urovne predpriyatiya, regiona, gosudarstva / N. V. Apatova, O. G. Blazhevich, T. K. Blokhina [i dr.] ; Sevastopol'skiy gosudarstvennyy universitet. — Simferopol' : Poliprint, 2023. — 280 s. — ISBN 978-5-605-10310-3. — EDN EROLLL.
8. Sbalansirovannaya sistema pokazateley [Tekst] : ot strategii k deystviyu / Robert S. Kaplan, Deyvid P. Norton ; [per. s angl. M. Pavlovoy]. — Moskva : Olimp-Biznes, 2008. — 294 s.
9. Sostavlyayushchiye strategicheskogo upravleniya finansovoy ustoychivost'yu khozyaystvuyushchikh sub'yektov / D. V. Bondarenko, Ye. I. Bondarenko, A. O. Kunskiy, N. A. Bunchuk // *Nauchnyy vestnik: finansy, banki, investitsii*. — 2024. — 1(66). — С. 76-88. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2024-1-76-88. — EDN IGTMTL.
10. Sokolov, B. I. Kovalev V. V. *Finansovyy menedzhment: teoriya i praktika* / B. I. Sokolov, S. V. Sokolova // *Vestnik Sankt-Peterburgskogo universiteta. Ekonomika*. — 2007. — 1. — С. 198-201. — EDN NSCKKB.
11. *Finansovyy menedzhment : Zadachi, delovyye situatsii i testy* / M. N. Kreynina. — Moskva : Delo i Servis, 1999. — 111 s.
12. *Finansovyy menedzhment : polnyy kurs : v 2 t.* / Yu. Brighem, L. Gapenski ; [per. s angl. pod red. V. V. Kovaleva]. — Sankt-Peterburg: Ekonomicheskaya shkola [i dr.], 1997. — Т. 1. — 1997. — XXX, 497 s.
13. *Finansovyy menedzhment v sfere biznesa : kollektivnaya monografiya* / Yu. N. Vorobyov, E. I. Vorobyova, L. M. Borshch [i dr.]. — Simferopol' : OOO «Antikva», 2017. — 632 s. — ISBN 978-5-9909795-9-8. — EDN ZDRPXL.
14. Ensuring economic security at different levels of economic management / D. D. Burkaltseva, M. N. Dudin, V. E. Reutov [et al.]. — Simferopol : POLIPRINT, 2018. — 194 p. — ISBN 978-5-6041133-5-6. — EDN UXEWGY.

11 2025

18 2025